

Public-Private Partnerships in Infrastructure Development in Africa: A Magic-Wand for Socio-Economic Growth and Development, *Mubarak T. Adekilekun* and Ching C. Gan***

(*Lecturer in the Department of Business Law, Faculty of Law, University of Ilorin, Nigeria.)

(**Formerly Associate Professor in the Faculty of Law, University of Malaya, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia. Dr Gan had retired and has joined **Southern University College, Johor Bahru, Malaysia** since 15 March 2017.)

“We have to construct a new world that is more equitable and responsive to the needs of the poor, mobilize all our people voluntarily to act together to achieve goals of reconstruction and development and to consolidate the practice of creating Public Private Partnership”

Thabo Mbeki, Former President of the Republic of South Africa.

Abstract: Infrastructure development is arguably the most important factor for economic development of any nation. Infrastructural facilities are the wheels which drive a nation’s economy. They provide the enabling environment for sustained and sustainable economic growth and helps in eradicating poverty. Africa faces huge infrastructure deficits and challenges. Generally speaking, the state of infrastructure development in Africa does not meet the requirements for economic development. A World Bank report stated that for Africa to fill the infrastructure gaps, an annual expenditure of \$93 Billion would be required within the next ten years. It is therefore apparent that governments alone, even at the best of times lack the capacity to provide for the infrastructure requirements of Africa. This clearly underscores the need for the participation of the private sector through Public Private Partnership which has been recognized as a global panacea for infrastructure deficits particularly in developing economies. It is therefore argued in this paper that PPP has the vast potentials to supplement Africa’s critical infrastructure gaps, where about 587 million people lack access to electricity, almost 300 million have no access to safe and clean water and about 93% of the population has no access to internet facilities. Public-Private Partnerships will ultimately boost the socio-economic growth and development in the continent and help it to achieve the Millennium Development Goals.

Keywords: Public-Private Partnership; Development; Private Sector; Infrastructure; Africa.

1.0 Introduction

The level of infrastructure development of any nation is directly proportional to the level of its economic development. Infrastructure development is arguably the most important factor for economic development. Infrastructural facilities are the wheels which drive a nation's economy. They provide the enabling environment for sustained and sustainable economic growth, job creation and helps in the eradication of poverty.

Roads and highways were considered to be the earliest human demand for infrastructure. The first world's known paved roads were laid in Egypt between 2600 and 2200 BC.¹ Indeed, it could not have been possible to build the pyramids without the roads on which the heavy limestone blocks were dragged. Also, stone paved roads were found in the city of Ur in the modern day Iraq since 4000 BC.² No doubt, civilization advanced or declined around the qualities of their road networks. The ancient Roman, Persian, Chinese and Indian civilizations built road networks that encouraged and advanced trade and commerce among those empires and also assisted them in the transportation of military equipment (Sawant 2010, 1).³ The technological advancement in the world today could not have been possible without the invention of electricity and its applications in the eighteen century by the great scientists like Benjamin Franklin, Alessandro Volta, Michael Faraday and many others.⁴

Today, Africa faces huge infrastructure deficits and challenges. No doubt, the state of infrastructure development in Africa does not meet the requirements for economic development and advancement. A World Bank report stated that for Africa to fill the infrastructure gaps, an annual expenditure of \$75 Billion would be required annually for the next ten years.⁵ It is therefore apparent that governments alone, even at the best of economic times, lack the capacity to provide for the infrastructure requirements and development of Africa. This clearly underscores the need for the participation of private sector through Public-Private Partnership which has been recognized as a global panacea for infrastructure deficits particularly in developing economies (Avery 2006, 1).⁶

As a result of the growing population and urbanization, citizens demand and require new roads, light rail networks, bridges and tunnels, water and sanitation plants, prisons, hospitals, schools, dams, roads, electricity, modern airport and air control system and other social and economic infrastructure. However, because of the inefficiencies, corruption, lack of skills and technical know-how that have characterized the provisions of public infrastructure through the traditional public procurement model, in the United Kingdom today, for example, the pertinent question which people tend to ask before any investment decision is taken is "Why not use a private finance solution?"⁷

¹Wildord, J. N. *World's Oldest Paved Road Found in Egypt*. Retrieved from . <http://www.nytimes.com/1994/05/08/world/world-s-oldest-paved-road-found-in-egypt.html>. Accessed 27th April, 2013.

² Roads and Highways, Encyclopedia Britannica, Encyclopedia Britannica online, www.britannica.com/EBchecked/topic/505109/road/71891/Ancient-roads-of-South-and-East-Asia. Accessed May 20 2013.

³ Sawant, R J. 2010. *Infrastructure investing: managing risks & rewards for pensions, insurance companies & endowments*. New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons. Page 1.

⁴William Gilbert, History of Electricity. Retrieved from <http://inventors.about.com/cs/inventorsalphabet/a/electricity.htm>, (accessed 20 May, 2013).

⁵ Fact Sheet: Infrastructure in Sub-Saharan. Africa <http://web.worldbank.org/WBSITE/EXTERNAL/COUNTRIES/AFRICAEXT/0,,contentMDK:21951811~pagePK:146736~piPK:146830~theSitePK:258644,00.html>. Accessed on 19th April, 2013.

⁶ Nicholas Avery, *Public-Private Partnerships: A Practical Analysis*, (London: Globe Publishing Ltd) 2006.P.1

⁷ *Ibid* at Page 2.

It is, therefore, argued in this paper that PPPs have vast economic and development potentials to supplement Africa's critical infrastructure gaps, where about 587 million people lack access to electricity,⁸ almost 300 million people have no access to safe and clean water⁹ and about 93% of the population has no access to internet facilities.¹⁰ Public-Private Partnerships will definitely and ultimately boost socio-economic growth and development in the continent and help it to strive for and achieve the Millennium Development Goals.

2.0 Meaning, Nature and Basic Concepts of Public-Private Partnerships

Public-Private Partnership (PPP) is a formal collaboration between the government and one or more private companies with the objective of procuring private capital, management, technology and other resources as a means of enhancing infrastructure service delivery. PPPs, through which private companies work with public sector to manage complex infrastructure projects and develop public services, are increasingly being used throughout the world as a solution to provide and speed up major public projects.

The term has also been defined¹¹ as a legally binding agreement between the government and private sector for the provision of infrastructure assets and efficient delivery of services that allocates responsibilities and business risks among the various partners. According to the World Bank,¹² there is no consensus on the definition of the term Public-Private partnerships. However, it is referred to as arrangements, ranging from medium to long term, between the public and private sectors whereby part of the services or works that fall under the domain of the public sector are provided by the private partners, with a detailed agreement for the delivery of public infrastructure and/ or services. The term has been defined to exclude privatization of utilities wherein there is a limited role for the public authority to perform.

Public-Private Partnerships occupy a middle position between Privatization and traditional Public Procurement. Privatization and Public-Private Partnerships reflect market principles and the two of them constitute a strategy for improving public management.¹³ PPPs are sometimes confused with privatization. Privatization connotes the permanent transfer of the public ownership of an asset to the private sector while in PPPs there is a continuing role to be performed by the public sector as partner in the ongoing relationship with the private sector (Ferguhason, et al, 2010, 9).¹⁴ Under the PPPs, accountability for the provision of the service is clearly a responsibility of the public sector that is in a continuing relationship with the private sector, while in Privatization, accountability for providing services will immediately be transferred to the private sector although the citizen would still have the right to complain to the government.

PPP is thus an alternative to the traditional public procurement system by providing the needed facilities to the public sector by using funding generated by the private sector. In PPPs, the government

⁸ See <http://www.worldenergyoutlook.org/resources/energydevelopment/accesstoelectricity/>

⁹ See http://www.unicef.org/wash/index_statistics.html. Accessed 17 May, 2013.

¹⁰ See <http://www.internetworldstats.com/stats1.htm>. Accessed 17 May, 2013.

¹¹ *An Introduction to Public- Private Partnerships* . Available at <<http://www.partnershipsbc.ca/pdf/An%20Introduction%20to%20P3%20-June03.pdf>>. Accessed 8 March, 2012.

¹² World Bank definition of Public-Private Partnerships <<http://ppp.worldbank.org/public-private-partnership/overview/what-are-public-private-partnerships>>. Accessed 8 March, 2012.

¹³ *Ibid.*

¹⁴ Farquharson, E., C. Torres de Mastle, E.R. Yescombe and E. Javier, 2010. *How to engage with the private sector in public-private partnerships in emerging markets*. Washington DC: The World Bank.

usually sets a target as to the quality and quantity it requires. The designing, financing, building and the operation of the project is left to the innovation of the private sector. This is because if the government carries out the design itself, it would also have to carry the risks resulting from faulty designs.

In most cases on the private sector side, a Special Purpose Vehicle (SPV) which is totally a consortium of financial institutions and private companies will be responsible for all the activities of PPPs including the coordination of the financing and service delivery. Most of the times, this will be a consortium which will have at least two shareholders. The SPV enters into an agreement with the public authority for the building of a new infrastructure or the management or upgrade of existing infrastructures. Under the PPP arrangement, the public authorities or public sector parties are known by different terms such as federal, central and regional, state, municipal, local, governmental institution, public agency or any other entity which is under the public-sector control. While the private sector party is normally a Special-Purpose Company which includes investors, lenders, and companies providing construction and operational services. According to Yescombe, the relationship between the parties is not really a partnership in the legal sense, but its contractual, being based on the terms of the PPP Contract.¹⁵

The way in which the infrastructure transactions in PPPs are structured necessitates payment of long term service fees usually over the life of the contract (20-30 years on the average) which is usually on a pre-agreed basis with the intention of repaying the cost expended in financing the project and to also give return to the investors (Yescombe 2007, 3).¹⁶ PPPs allow public authority to retain ownership while engaging the private sector to perform functions such as financing, designing, constructing, maintaining and operating infrastructure like roads or providing basic services like water and electricity. Both parties stand to benefit from the contractual agreement.

Public-Private Partnerships will therefore help African governments in the provision of both social and economic infrastructures which will help to bolster their economies. This may either be in the provision of new infrastructures or in the rehabilitation of the existing ones. The objectives of a typical PPP arrangement in Nigeria is the mission to contribute to the economic integration of the country, accelerate its economic growth and sustainable development, engender and sustain private sector collaboration in traditionally public sector projects and also expand local access to international market thereby ensuring a deeper economic integration with the global world.

3.0 History of Public-Private Partnerships

Public-Private Partnerships have been used as concession to finance infrastructure projects in the nineteenth century (Ngwachi et al, 2011, 1:2).¹⁷ One of the earliest and best known water projects was the Suez Canal which was managed by the private sector until it was nationalized in the 1950s.¹⁸ Tolling commenced in the United States between 1789 and 1900.¹⁹ Over 2,000 private companies operated turnpikes in Ohio, New York, Michigan and Albany as a result of inadequate highways that

¹⁵ *Ibid.*

¹⁶ Yescombe, E. R, 2007. *Public-private partnerships principles of policy and finance*. Oxford: Elsevier Publishing Ltd.

¹⁷ Nyagwachi, Josiah & Smallwood, John, South African 2011. Public Private Partnerships (PPP) Projects. *Journal of Construction Vol. 1, No 2*.

¹⁸ *Ibid.*

¹⁹ The private companies that build these roads were stage companies, miners, and ranchers who built the roads, at least in part, to attract business for their primary investments. See further http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Toll_roads_in_the_United_States. Accessed 22 May, 2013.

existed at that time.²⁰ In the 1960s, Spain embarked on its motorways programme which was financed by the private sector because of the inadequacy of the national budget to meet the infrastructure demands of the country at that time.

The energy crises of the 1970s led to the collapse of most of these private companies which necessitated the nationalization of some of these enterprises. Also at that time, the Labour Government in Britain was of the view that the market economy was very unfair and imperfect. Leaving the means of production, distribution and exchange to market forces was considered inequitable and that this would lead to the marginalization and impoverishment of the people.²¹

However, changed economic condition saw the process being reversed in the 1980s when it became clear that governments as entrepreneurs had not succeeded. Most of their investments in commerce had been a colossal waste of government revenue. Interestingly, the philosophical position in the United Kingdom had begun to shift. Then, the Conservative Government of Margaret Thatcher had defeated the Labour government of Sir Harold Wilson.²² Both Margaret Thatcher and Ronald Reagan of the United States were of the firm view that Government had no business in commerce.²³ The only role of Government was to provide a conducive and an enabling environment for entrepreneurs to flourish.²⁴

Also in the 1980s, China under the visionary leadership of Deng Xiaoping radically pursued a policy of private enterprise which changed his country's policy of overdependence on failed state enterprises.²⁵ This paradigm shift ushered in a new era of positive economic outcomes that continue till today. His famous Chinese saying was "***don't care what colour a cat is as long as it catches mice***" which has unraveled china's economic miracles.

South Africa, Nigeria and Ghana²⁶ among other African countries have also adopted the PPP initiative. In 1999, the first major legislation on Public Private Partnerships in the country was enacted. These provisions are set out in Treasury Regulation 16 issued by the National Treasury in accordance with the Public Finance Management Act, 1999 PFMA²⁷ which for the first time established a dedicated PPP unit within the treasury in the year 2000. The main objectives of this Act are to enhance sound financial management and maximize service delivery through the effective and efficient utilization of limited resources.²⁸

Former President Olusegun Obasanjo²⁹ in his assessment of the decline in Nigeria's public infrastructures stated that these infrastructures suffer from fundamental problems of defective capital structure, excessive bureaucratic control or intervention in appropriate technology, gross incompetence and mismanagement, blatant corruption and crippling complacency which monopoly

²⁰ *Ibid.*

²¹ See *The Legal Dynamics of Privatisation in Nigeria*, Retrieved from www.babalakinandco.com. Accessed 15 February, 2011.

²² In May 1979, Labour Party lost the general election to the Conservatives and Margaret Thatcher became Britain's first female prime minister.

²³ Both the late Margaret Thatcher and Ronald Reagan championed the concept of Neo-liberalism in the 1980s.

²⁴ The government can provide good investment laws that will protect the interest of both foreign and local investors.

²⁵ He abandoned many orthodox communist doctrines and attempted to incorporate elements of the free-enterprise system into the China economy.

²⁶ In order to give effect to the provisions of Article 36 (2) (b) of the 1992 Ghanaian Constitution,²⁶ which gives private individuals the right to participate in economic activities, the government, after a wider consultation established the Public Investment Division (PID) within the Ministry of Finance and Economic Planning to regulate private sector participation in public infrastructure delivery. This was part of the government support to bolster private sector participation in infrastructure development through the PPP initiative.

²⁷ Act No 1 of 1999, (As Amended) by Act No 29 of 1999.

²⁸ PFMA available at <http://www.treasury.gov.za/legislation/PFMA/default.aspx>, (last accessed on 21 March 2014).

²⁹ Former President of the Federal Republic of Nigeria from 1999-2007.

engenders.³⁰ Nigeria has since 2005 adopted the PPP initiative as a solution to its huge infrastructure gap. The Infrastructure Concession and Regulatory Establishment Act of 2005 was enacted to provide the legal and regulatory Frameworks for PPPs to thrive in Nigeria.³¹

In recent times, a worldwide movement has taken place in respect of Public-Private Partnerships (Grimsey, 2007, 2).³² The main aim of this innovation is to introduce the effective functioning principles of the private sector into the public administration (Hammami, 2006, 5).³³ This move was necessitated by the need to reduce inefficiencies, wastages in public spending, lack of managerial skills and to attract private capital in the provision of public infrastructure.

4.0 The Current State of Infrastructures in Africa

The record of African infrastructure has been both impressive and disappointing. Impressive in the sense that in the 1960s when most African nations got their political independence, infrastructure was almost non-existent. Upon independence, most African leaders swung into action to provide critical infrastructure to their nations. Infrastructure started flourishing because as at that time, most African governments wanted to showcase to their people what is called “the fruits of independence”.³⁴ This was made possible by the commitments of those leaders at that time and with the help of the multinational institutions.

However, since the late 1980s, the state of infrastructure has started deteriorating. In spite of urbanization and industrialization, the existing infrastructures were not upgraded or modernized to meet the needs of the growing population. The combination of poor management, poor policies and state monopolies, absence of effective maintenance and lack of re-investment had led to deterioration of infrastructure and had occasioned massive losses. In the process, everyone had become a loser, the consumers, the operators, and the state as well as other sectors of the economy. Within just over two decades, infrastructure in most African countries has now become a hindrance rather than a facilitator to nation’s development. It is, therefore, important at this juncture to briefly analyze the current situation of infrastructure in Africa.

4.1 Electricity Infrastructure

Power blackout is a regular phenomenon in most African cities, towns and villages with negative impacts on the quality of lives and economic development. Most of the electricity equipment that were erected in the 1950s and 1960s are ageing and operating at a sub-optimal level due to lack of maintenance.³⁵ Countries in Sub-Sahara Africa are still plagued with electricity crisis due to unreliable supplies, insufficient generating capacity and high tariffs being paid by the consumers.

³⁰http://wiki.answers.com/Q/What_are_the_problems_of_Nigeria_enterprises. Accessed on 21 June, 2014.

³¹ This Act is now in the Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2010.

³² Grimsey D and K.L. Mervyn. 2007. *Public private partnerships: the worldwide revolution in infrastructure provision and project finance*. Massachusetts: Edward Elger Publishing Limited.

³³ Hammami, M, J. Ruhashyankiko and E.B Yehoue. 2006. *Determinants of public private partnerships in infrastructure*. Washington DC: International Monetary Fund.

³⁴ Shemmy Simuyemba , 2000. Linking Africa through regional infrastructure. *Economic Research Paper No 64*. Abidjan: African Development Bank.

³⁵ Africa’s Energy Situation. Retrieved from www.desertec-africa.org/index.php?option=com_content&view, (accessed 4 May, 2013).

Electricity generation in the region is the lowest compared to all other regions in the world, whereas the average tariff being paid by the consumers doubles that of other regions in the world.³⁶ The total electricity generation of 48 countries that make up the Sub-Saharan Africa (with a combined population of about 800 million people) stands at about 68 Gigawatts (GW), which is far lesser than that of Spain alone (with a population of 45 million) which generated about 100 Gigawatts (GW) in 2010.³⁷ Without South Africa, the total falls to a mere 28 GW, equivalent to the installed capacity of Argentina.³⁸

In Sub-Saharan Africa apart from South Africa, power consumption per capital per year is put at 124 kilowatt hours. This is barely enough to power just one 100 Watts bulb for just three hours in a day.³⁹ Taiwan, Singapore and Malaysia that were almost in the same level with some of these African countries in the 1980s can now boast of 9,502, 7,695 and 3,215 Kilowatt hour per capital respectively.⁴⁰

Nigeria is a country of about 167 Million people with enormous oil and gas reserves, as at year 2014, power generation stood at about 4,000 Megawatts. It is estimated that the country's current electricity demand is well above 15,000 Megawatts which on a per capita basis is still less than one tenth of that of South Africa and two and half times less than Egypt.⁴¹ About \$US50 Billion Dollars was disbursed on electricity within Fourteen years⁴² leading to generation of only about 1,000 Megawatts⁴³ from 3000 Megawatts in 1999 to 4000 Megawatts in 2014. Mismanagement and underinvestment in this sector are not unconnected to the fact that since the country's independence in 1960, electricity generation and distribution has been an exclusive preserve of the Federal Government. The same unsatisfactory state of affairs exists in Kenya, Rwanda, Sierra Leone, and Mali and so on.⁴⁴ Unreliable and epileptic power supply has been a perennial problem of these Sub-Saharan African countries for decades.⁴⁵

4.2 Water and Sanitation

According to the United Nations Environmental report, it is estimated that in Africa, over 300 million people lack access to clean and safe drinking water.⁴⁶ Averagely, it is estimated that women and children in Sub-Saharan countries walk for about six kilometers daily in search of drinkable water.⁴⁷ The World Health Organization has estimated that not less than 40 billion hours are spent annually in

³⁶ Eberhard, A, V. Foster, C. Briceño-Garmendia, F. Ouedraogo, D. Camos, and M. Shkaratan. 2008. *Underpowered: the state of the power sector in sub-saharan Africa*, Washington DC: The World Bank.

³⁷ Electricity infrastructure in Spain. Retrieved from http://ec.europa.eu/energy/gas_electricity/doc/es_energy_market_2011_en.pdf. (accessed 22 May, 2013).

³⁸ *Ibid.*

³⁹ Fact Sheet: Infrastructure in Sub-Saharan Africa. Retrieved from <http://web.worldbank.org/WBSITE/EXTERNAL/COUNTRIES/AFRICAEXT/0,,contentMDK:21951811~pagePK:146736~piPK:146830~theSitePK:258644,00.html>, (accessed 22 May, 2013).

⁴⁰ Electricity Consumption per Capital. Retrieved from <http://www.indexmundi.com/g/r.aspx?v=81000>, (accessed 22 May, 2013).

⁴¹ Nigeria's Power Situation: Where are The IPPS? <http://www.Ayakaonline.Com/Politics/Nigerias-Power-Situation-Where-Are-The-Ipps/>, (accessed 23 May, 2013).

⁴² This covers a period between 1999-2013.

⁴³ State of Electricity Supply in Nigeria. <http://thenationonlineng.net/new/columnists/state-of-electricity-supply-in-nigeria/>, (accessed 28 May, 2013).

⁴⁴ Energy Statistics: Electricity Production Per Capital. Retrieved from http://www.nationmaster.com/graph/ene_ele_pro_percap-energy-electricity-production-per-capita. Accessed 23 May, 2013.

⁴⁵ Enabling Private Sector Participation in Electricity Generation. Retrieved from <http://www.gsb.uct.ac.za/files/Kenya.pdf>. Accessed 23 May, 2013.

⁴⁶ <http://www.unep.org/>

⁴⁷ Water and Sanitation. Retrieved from <http://www.one.org/c/us/issuebrief/99/>. Accessed 23 May, 2013.

search of safe and drinkable water. That is equivalent to a year of labor for the entire workforce in France. African countries have advanced various reasons for not being able to meet the challenges of providing clean water and sanitary environment and also for not implementing the integrated water management policies.⁴⁸ The reason advanced by Sierra Leone, Nigeria and Congo-Brazzaville at the World Water Week held in Stockholm is that they do not have formal water policy.⁴⁹ São Tomé and Príncipe stated that the necessary laws and regulations are not in place, while it was asserted by the representative of Cameroon that the country does not have people who can champion the cause of providing water. About 25 African countries including Rwanda, Swaziland, Mozambique and Namibia among others attribute this problem to inadequate human capacity. Congo-Brazzaville stated that it could not get interested private sector, while to Burundi, incessant changes in administration has been identified as the major cause.

The effects of lack of access to water and sanitation have a macroeconomic impact on the continent⁵⁰ and the benefits of improving access to water and sanitation are very enormous. Achieving the water and sanitation Millennium Development Goals would increase the yearly economic benefits of the continent to about \$22 billion.⁵¹ This is because, it is estimated that every \$1 dollar judiciously spent on this sector will bring a return of about \$8 dollars in saved time, and it will help in reducing health costs and thereby increasing productivity. If the MDG targets on water and sanitation are met by 2015, national governments in sub-Saharan Africa could save about 12% of annual public health expenditures.

4.3 ICT infrastructure

Access to internet facilities is low in Africa and far less than any other region in the world.⁵² As at 2013, only 7% of the total population has access to internet facilities which amounts to only half of what is obtainable in South East Asia and the Pacific.⁵³ According to the International Telecommunications Union data, only five countries in the Sub-Saharan Africa have internet penetration rates exceeding 20 percent.⁵⁴ The Seychelles has the highest internet penetration per population with 43% than any other sub-Saharan Africa; Nigeria, with 48 million internet users has the highest number of internet users in Africa followed by Egypt, Morocco, Kenya and South Africa in that order. Southern Sudan has the lowest penetration rate of 0%, followed by Ethiopia with 1.1%, and then Congo DR, and Somalia with 1.2% rates.⁵⁵

Although in recent times, the performance of Africa's mobile networks has radically improved, the telecommunications industries all over the world have also evolved. Internet broadband is now considered as central to a long term economic development strategies of a nation. In some countries in Africa, internet broadband is not available and where available, it is highly expensive and far more

⁴⁸ Water and Sanitation Still not Top Priorities for African Governments

<http://www.guardian.co.uk/global-development/2012/aug/30/water-sanitation-priorities-african-governments>. Accessed 23 May, 2013.

⁴⁹ World Water Week Stockholm. Retrieved from <http://www.worldwaterweek.org/sa/node.asp?node=1349>. Accessed 23 May, 2013.

⁵⁰ *Ibid.*

⁵¹ See Supra Note 38.

⁵² Sub-Saharan Africa. Retrieved from <https://opennet.net/research/regions/ssafrika>. Accessed 23 May, 2013.

⁵³ The World in 2013, ICT Facts and Figures. <http://www.itu.int/en/ITU-D/Statistics/Documents/facts/ICTFactsFigures2013.pdf>. Accessed 24 May, 2013.

⁵⁴ These countries are Cape Verde, Kenya, Nigeria Sao Tome and Principe and Sycheless.

⁵⁵ See <http://www.internetworldstats.com/stats1.htm>. Accessed 26 May, 2013.

beyond what the majority of the people can afford (Mark, et al, 2011,1).⁵⁶ In 2013, the total fixed-broadband penetration rates for developing countries are 6.1% and less than 1% in Sub-Saharan Africa.

4.4 Road Infrastructure

The condition of roads in Africa continent ranges from fair to poor. There are relatively very few roads in good condition. In Nigeria for example, the existing network of highways in the country is not only inadequate but also largely in a deplorable state. In Kenya, between January and April 2013, over 1,000 deaths have been recorded as a result of road accidents.⁵⁷ The situation in most Sub-Saharan countries is not so different. Rural Africa has only 34% of access roads compared to about 90% in the developed world.⁵⁸ About 80% of the cargo loads in sub-Saharan Africa are taken through the roads. Good national and regional transportation links are very vital to the governmental policies of reducing poverty and hunger.⁵⁹

5.0 Reasons for Private Sector Involvement in Infrastructure Development

There are many reasons why the government needs to collaborate with the private sector in the delivery of public goods and services. It is not in doubt as stated earlier in this work that budgetary constraints and inefficiencies on the part of government are among the reasons. Afeikhena Jerome, listed some of the reasons why government corporations have failed to provide adequate services to the people. He put the reasons succinctly as:⁶⁰

“underpricing; low productivity; poor service quality; long queues and large portions of the population without access to basic services; lack of transparency; and damaging political interference in the operations of these infrastructure entities.”

These reasons have been grouped and discussed under five major sub-headings. They are:

5.1 Attracting Private Capital Investment

Governments are attracted by the benefits of mobilizing private capital. The estimated demand for public infrastructure is huge and sometimes above the entire budget projection of a nation. The government alone cannot provide these basic infrastructure because of non-availability of funds. A World Bank report stated that for Africa to fill the infrastructure gaps, an annual expenditure of US\$75 Billion (US\$38 billion of investment and a further US\$37 billion in operations and maintenance) would

⁵⁶ Mark D. J., R.M. Williams and M. Minges. 2011. *Africa's ICT infrastructure: building on a mobile revolution*. Washington DC: The World Bank.

⁵⁷ See: Stop! The crippling state of Kenya's killer roads reported in The Daily Nation Newspapers of May 27, 2013. Retrieved from <http://www.nation.co.ke/Features/DN2/Accideaths/-/957860/1755208/-/kmxusj/-/index.html>. Accessed 27 May, 2013

⁵⁸ African Development Bank, 2010.

⁵⁹ See: Roads funded by EU left to fall apart in sub-Saharan Africa. <http://www.guardian.co.uk/global-development/2013/jan/18/roads-funded-eu-sub-saharan-africa>. Accessed 25 May, 2013.

⁶⁰ Jerome A, 'Infrastructure privatisation and liberalisation in Africa: The quest for the holy grail or coup de grace?', September 2004, Johannesburg: National Institute for Economic Policy; paper presented at '4th Mediterranean Seminar on International Development, University of the Balearic Islands, Palma de Mallorca, Spain.

be required annually within the next ten years.⁶¹ It is obvious that this huge capital deficit cannot be raised through public funds alone.

A typical example of a project financed with the support of the private sector is the R2.6 Billion PPP project for the N3 and N4 toll road linking the South African provinces of Gauteng, Limpopo and Mpumalanga to the port of Maputo in Mozambique. Mozambique lacked the required funds to rehabilitate and maintain its own part of the N4 highway, the railway line and the ports which were long damaged as a result of the civil war that ravaged that country.⁶² As at 1997, the total estimation of South Africa's requirement to fix its roads was estimated to be R37 billion, both governments were thus in need of funds to finance and maintain this all important infrastructure. As a result of this, the PPP approach was then resorted to, and with the cooperation of the private sector, the project became a reality.

Therefore, harnessing private capital can help the government to speed up the delivery of public infrastructure without delay. The banking and finance markets have moved in to accommodate the needs of PPP transactions. We have seen extraordinary change in the duration of time for which financial institutions are willing to lend. Loan maturities of 10 to 12 years were unusual in the 1980s and 1990s; now we see repayment periods of 30 to 35 years (and beyond).⁶³ In the case of PPPs, there are repayment periods of 25-30 years and even beyond. This is because the manner the infrastructure projects are structured guarantees a high degree of certainty of stable cash flow in these projects. Also, Pension Funds Administrators are also becoming interested in long term fixed-income investment which PPPs provide.

5.2 It increases efficiency and the use of resources

Scarce public resources are not being used efficiently by most governments. Also, because of the poor incentives for efficiency, the public sector is not rightly positioned to efficiently build and operate infrastructure. Combining such incentives in the operation and management of the public infrastructure through the private sector is therefore necessary. Typically, private sector operators enter into such transactions with the intention of maximizing profits which are geared majorly by increased efficiency in investment and operations. If the PPPs are designed in such a manner as to allow the operator realize this goal, the efficiency of the infrastructure services will be achieved.

According to Philippe Burger,⁶⁴ he stated that one major reason why it is better to adopt PPP instead of privatization is where effectiveness, rather than efficiency, is also an aim of the government. A policy becomes effective where the aim of government with respect to which it was conceived is achieved, irrespective of whether the aim is carried out in an efficient manner or not. Achieving the result is the aim, and such aim is carried out effectively.

⁶¹ Fact Sheet: Infrastructure in Sub-Saharan Africa. <http://web.worldbank.org/WBSITE/EXTERNAL/COUNTRIES/AFRICAEXT/0,,contentMDK:21951811~pagePK:146736~piPK:146830~theSitePK:258644,00.html>. Accessed 19 April, 2013.

⁶² Civil war began in Mozambique in 1977 and ended in 1992. During this time, most of the critical infrastructure were damaged and this led to a serious infrastructure deficit.

⁶³ Nicholas Avery. 2006. *Public-private partnerships: a practical analysis*. London: Globe Publishing Ltd.

⁶⁴ See the Dedicated PPP Unit of the Southern African National Treasury.

There is no doubt that the governments have access to more funding than the private sector, the efficiency gains from the private sector participation may in the long run outweigh the extra financial cost expended.⁶⁵

The greater efficiency of the private sector can be linked to the following factors:

- (i) The private sector's commercial approaches to problem solving with serious focus on cost-effectiveness leads to the rationalization of cost of labour and materials;
- (ii) By allowing less politically oriented decision-making will surely lead to better governance and it will improve accountability; and
- (iii) Improving competition and transparency will greatly reduce the opportunity for corrupt practices and it will reveal those costs that were hitherto hidden.⁶⁶

5.3 Reform of the sectors through a reallocation of roles, incentives, and accountability

Once risks, roles and responsibilities are reallocated, there is a tendency that efficiency and accountability will be assured. Also, corruption which is common in conventional procurement setting will be greatly reduced thereby enhancing greater output.

5.4 Technology, Innovation and Know-how

By involving the private sector, access to new technologies and experienced management not currently available through public monopoly could be tapped into and reaped. This will include access to skills and those technologies and know-how which were otherwise not known to the public sector. These technologies may even be developed for those projects specifically which would not have been developed under the traditional procurement system.

5.5 Transparency and Anti-corruption

One of the major challenges facing public procurement in Africa is corruption, which is a major threat to transparency. It does not only threaten but it undermines the legitimacy of the corrupted government.⁶⁷ Unfortunately, in the African countries, there were reported cases of scandals involving major companies and public officials which have been exposed by the media, as a consequence of bribery and other crimes committed during procurement procedures and other government contracts.⁶⁸ Corruption in the procurement process in Africa is not insignificant because globalization has brought it across borders.

Openness and good governance will lead to equality in the treatment of the investors and it will promote fair competition. Lack of transparency and good governance, therefore, increases the

⁶⁵OECD. Principles for Private Sector Participation in Infrastructure. Retrieved from <http://www.oecd.org/daf/inv/investment-policy/38309896.pdf>, (accessed 28 May, 2013).

⁶⁶ Jeffrey Delmon, Page 14.

⁶⁷ OECD, 2007, *Integrity in Public Procurement. Good Practice from A-Z*. OECD Publishers.

⁶⁸ For example, a US based company KBR Inc was charged in a USD 180 Million to bribe Nigerian officials in order to secure about USD Six Billion worth of contract. After being arraigned in the United States, KBR Inc agreed to pay USD 402 Million fine to terminate the investigation.

likelihood of bribery and corruption, increases costs and reduces competition and the quality of the output. PPPs, therefore, provide the opportunity to reduce corruption and promote good governance in the process of implementation.

6.0 Achieving Socio-Economic Sustainability through the PPP Initiative

In this day and age, the concept of sustainable development is no longer new (Adeoye, 2012, 127).⁶⁹ Its impacts and usage have traversed all facets of human life. The United Nations has defined the concept as *“Development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs”*

African continent lags behind other continents in terms of development. It was noted by Sirleaf and Radelet that the past three decades has been disastrous for Africa because most of her people have been inflicted with poverty (Sirleaf and Radelet, 2008, 1).⁷⁰ Poverty is said to be caused by lack of access to income and capital assets, lack of political voice and incidence of natural disasters. Of the three, the first two are man-made accounting for the highest challenge of our time. Interestingly, Africa is one of the least continents affected by natural disasters. Indeed, it is one of the most naturally endowed continents in the world. Notwithstanding these God-given endowments, we remain the most backward continent as we are unable to put our acts together and harness our resources for the collective good of the citizens.

Harnessing private sector investment, skills and efficiency in the provision of infrastructure will ultimately lead to sustainable development. The Millennium Development Goals and the vision 20:20 may be unrealistic without the involvement of the private sector in development. For example, achieving safe water and sanitation for all by the year 2015 will require private sector investment and improvement in the technical and managerial performances.

It is important at this juncture to cite few examples of projects executed through PPPs and how they have alleviated the sufferings of the people and contributed to development. They are:

1. In Gabon for example, PPPs have been used to provide water and electricity to the two main cities of Port-Gentil and Libreville.⁷¹ In 1997, the government signed a 20 year concession contract with SEEG, with a capital value of US\$135 million. This concession contract has been a success and it was the first real output driven water project in Africa. Through PPP in water project, more than half of the Gabonese population now has access to safe water.
2. In Durban, South Africa, the Inkosi Albert Luthuli Central Hospital was contracted to the private sector for 15 years under the Design, Finance, Build, Operate and transfer (DFBOT).⁷² Under the arrangement, the Impilo Consortium will upgrade and manage the facilities and information technology of an 846-bed state-of-the-heart referral hospital. The capital value of this project is put at US\$746 million. This hospital is well equipped and provides services to

⁶⁹ Adeoye, R. A., P.E. Bondzi-Simpson, W.O. Egbewole, M.A. Etudaiye and O.A. Olayunji eds, 2012. *The rights of indigenous People to Sustainable Development in Africa-The Case of Gbagyi People of Nigeria in Law and Sustainable Development in Africa*. Surrey: Grosevenor House Publishing.

⁷⁰ Sirleaf E.J and s. Radelet, 2008. *The good news out of Africa: Democracy, Stability and the Renewal of Growth and Development, speech delivered at the Centre for Global Development*.

⁷¹ Ferguharson, E, C. Torres de Mastle ,E.R Yescombe and E. Javier. 2010. *How to Engage with the Private Sector in Public Private Partnerships*. Washington DC: The World Bank.

⁷² See PPP Quarterly, A publication of the PPP Unit, National Treasury South Africa. Number 28 of February, 2009.

the people of KwaZulu Natal and the Eastern Cape Province. The general opinion has been that PPP through which this hospital was built has delivered a quality service which could not have been achieved by the government alone.

3. In Manila, Philippines, as a result of lack of access to drinkable water, the government engaged the private sector through Public Private Partnerships to provide access to water in the Eastern Zone of Metro Manila. The contract has a capital value of US\$17 million. Since the water project was completed, the company has met all its obligations regarding water supply. In fact, the water project currently serves more than 5.1 million people and the company has increased its coverage of 24hours water supply to about 98 percent of the area.
4. In Lagos Nigeria, in an attempt to eliminate the severe traffic jam along Lekki-Epe Expressway, the Lagos State Government granted a concession contract to the Lekki Concession Company (LCC) to design, construct, finance, and operate the toll road project. The Upgrade and expansion of the 49.36 km road will be maintained by the LCC for a period of 30 years.⁷³ The capital value is estimated to be US\$450 million. Since the completion of construction work in 2012, motorists have felt highly relieved because the road is fully operational.

7.0 Does Law has any Role to Play in Development?

Where a nation seeks to achieve sustainable development, legal intervention is not only necessary but also inevitable. But the question is intervening to do what? There is no doubt that both the *existence* and *enforcement* of the law are both indispensable (Bondzi-Simpson, 2012, 422) .⁷⁴ Therefore, if a nation has set a developmental target for itself and has not been met, the law must ask itself three (3) questions. The first question is-- "*are there applicable rules and regulations that govern the matter under consideration?*" Where it is found that no rule exists, then there is what is called **availability gap**. Where there are rules applicable to the subject matter, then the next question goes thus: "*Are the rules adequate to address all conceivable issues touching on the subject matter?*" If the answer is in the affirmative, then there is no problem; but if it is in the negative, then there is an **adequacy gap**. Thirdly, if there are rules and the rules are adequate, the question is-- "*are they being enforced in such a way that strict compliance is achieved?*" If there is enforcement, then no problem, but if they are not, then there is an **enforcement gap**.

Therefore, the role of law in achieving sustainable development cannot be over emphasized. Legal intervention is not only necessary but indispensable in achieving sustainable development. African governments should therefore adopt a legal intervention that will tackle the **availability, adequacy and enforcement gaps** that ought to be filled by the law in order to achieve sustainable development in the continent.

8.0 Solutions/ Recommendations for African Governments

⁷³ See Lekki-Epe Concession Projects. Retrieved from

http://www.lagosstateppp.gov.ng/projects/project_portfolio/project_in_construction.asp. Accessed 28 May, 2013.

⁷⁴ P.E. Bondzi-Simpson. 2012. *Green Jurisprudence: Laws Place in Sustainable Development*, in Law and Sustainable Development in Africa, edited by Bondzi-Simpson P.E, Egbewole W.O, Etudaiye M.A, Olatunji AO. Surrey: Grosvenor House Publishing Limited. P422.

The following recommendations are important for African governments to fill the infrastructure challenges confronting the continent through the Public-Private Partnership initiatives:

1. African governments are greatly encouraged to explore the opportunities provided by the private sector which are: the availability of large capital to fund and maintain infrastructure projects; skills and technological know-how; competence in the proper and efficient management of resources as well as the accountability and transparency to drive the continent to achieve sustainable development. Where the necessary infrastructure is provided through the public-private cooperation, definitely, it will boost African economy and promote regional integration. This will also lead to an increase in the standard of living and reduction in the rate of crimes within the continent.
2. African governments should adopt a uniform legal and regulatory regime to address PPPs transactions in the continent. Despite the high level of infrastructure development in Europe, the European Commission, having realized the benefits of having single legal and regulatory regimes for concession contracts, has on 13th day of April, 2011 declared its intention to adopt a uniform legislative framework to govern PPP contracts in the community. This will help the EC in order to further boost growth and strengthens confidence in the investors. Presently, the award of PPP contracts in Africa is subject to a limited number of secondary law provisions which are applicable in the few countries that have legislative framework for PPPs. This gap will limit the access of African business from the international borders and, therefore, lack of access to other markets has led to uneven development within the continent.
3. Governments sometimes find it difficult to establish an effective framework that gives investors sufficient confidence. Investors will be most concerned if there is uncertainty in the law and lack of political independence of the regulatory agencies. In developing countries, which Africa is part of, successful implementation of private infrastructure investment requires a careful review of the entire business environments and, if necessary, reform of the policy framework underlying it. New institutional structures often need to be designed, legislations need to be enacted or amended and regulatory oversight functions need to be established and strengthened.
4. Political commitment on the part of governments is very important. It is one thing to have sound regulations for PPPs, and it is another thing for the governments and their agencies to be committed to making PPPs work. Unless governments and their agencies are absolutely determined that PPPs succeed, there may be sufficient vested interests in the country against PPPs that would ensure that the government's initiative to promote PPPs fail. In addition to this, the government should also provide political guarantees to investors where appropriate. In Nigeria, for example, despite the fact that there are laws in place to regulate PPP transactions, the Federal Government has not shown enough commitments to support the initiative and that is why no much success has been recorded since the inception of the scheme.
5. The success of Public-Private Partnerships is dependent on mutual trust between government officials and private sector executives. Also, building and maintaining public confidence promotes the integrity of the partnerships. Trusts and confidence are, therefore, the

hallmarks of this kind of partnership. Where there is trust and confidence, the private sector will be willing to invest its capital because of the integrity of the partnership programme.

6. Governments should develop the necessary capacity (institutional, negotiating, legal etc.) to handle PPP projects at the national state/provincial and the local government levels. This is because PPP are very complex in nature. Public-Private Partnerships require a host of competent and skilled staff to successfully handle the complex PPP transactions in order to achieve value for money. The required areas of competencies include human resources, project management; financial analysis, legislative and regulatory knowledge, legal matrix of PPPs and insurance. Therefore, the necessary competencies should be deployed in order to achieve the desired goals.
7. Governments should develop laws and policies aimed at encouraging private sectors to perform their corporate social responsibilities. The stakeholders in the business communities should now be more concerned with how they are perceived by their host communities and how they project their corporate success image on the scale of social crusade as contributors to social development and economic enhancement partners. They should be more and more concerned with how to contribute their quota to the development of the community.

9.0 Conclusion

Economic activities and other social services cannot function effectively in a nation without the modern and adequate infrastructure facilities in place. The present state of infrastructure in Africa does not support the continent's drive for economic development. Africa cannot hope to achieve the Millennium Development Goals and take its rightful place in the global economy without a modern, sound and efficient infrastructure system. As a result of globalization which has removed barriers to a nation's border, it will be increasingly difficult for Africa to remain competitive if its infrastructure development continues to perform at a sub optimal level. More serious and sustained efforts are needed to give more impetus to infrastructure development in Africa in coming years. Development, eradication of poverty and securing peace and prosperity for the people are achievable goals provided that all the stakeholders play their respective role seriously and accordingly.

Today, there is a worldwide revolution for infrastructure provision through the Public-Private Partnership initiative. This paradigm shift to PPPs from other procurement methods can help African nations to achieve value for money and sufficient transfer of risks to the private sector. Properly coordinated and well managed partnerships between the private sector and the governments will help African nations to achieve MDGs and sustainable development and therefore can take their rightful place in the global economies. It is in fact a modest and achievable development initiative provided that everything is put in place to make it happen!

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